

Influence of three carbamate pesticides on Mn and Fe status of saline sodic soil of Aligarh. Part-I

O. P. Bansal

Chemistry Department, D. S. College, Aligarh-202 001, India

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The present study envisages the effect of different doses of three carbamate pesticides, namely, methyl *N,N'*-dimethyl-*N*-(methylcarbamoyl)oxythiooxamimidate (Oxamyl) (I), *S*-ethyl-*N*-(methylcarbamoyl)oxythioacetamidate (II) and *N*-phenyl(1-ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate (III) on the change in concentration of different forms of Mn and Fe status; change in pH, EC and redox potential (E_h) of a saline soil over a period of 90 days. The correlation coefficients amongst them are also calculated. The results reveal that there is an optimum effect on the water-soluble, exchangeable, active Mn; exchangeable and available Fe; EC and E_h , with 0.25 g kg⁻¹ soil of pesticide I; 0.2 g kg⁻¹ of pesticide II and 0.3 g kg⁻¹ soil of pesticide III after 30 days of application. The pH was found to decrease with the time upto 30 days. The water-soluble, exchangeable, active Mn; exchangeable, available Fe, E_h and EC were positively correlated with each other, while negatively correlated with reducible Mn and pH. The results have been explained on the basis of chemical and microbial activity of pesticides in soils. The activity of carbamate pesticides is in the order, II > I > III.

Large quantities of pesticides reach the soil either by direct application or as run off from treated crop plants¹. Once in the soil, pesticides influence the growth and activity of the microorganism which are largely responsible for the maintenance of soil fertility². Microorganisms mineralize, oxidize, reduce and immobilize plant nutrient ions in soil and also indirectly influence their solubilities³. Any compound that alters the number or activity of microorganisms, influence the soil fertility and plant growth⁴. Influence of organic pesticides such as HCH, nemagon 2,4-D, telone, etc. on the trace element status in soil has been studied by Singhal *et al.*⁵⁻⁷. McLay and Robson⁸ studied the influence of chlorosulfuron and diclofopmethyl on the uptake and utilization of zinc by wheat. However, there is dearth of information regarding carbamate pesticides.

In view of great importance of the micronutrients in plant metabolism and the increased use of carbamate pesticides for high yield of crops, it was worthwhile to examine the effect of three carbamate pesticides (methyl-*N,N'*-dimethyl-*N*-(methylcarbamoyl)oxythiooxamimidate (Oxamyl), *S*-ethyl-*N*-(methylcarbamoyl)oxythioacetamidate and *N*-phenyl(1-ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate) on different forms of Mn and Fe status and on population of soil microorganisms in saline soil of Aligarh district.

Results and Discussion

Date of Table 1 denote that the microbial population (fungi, bacterial and actinomycetes) got increased by addition of lower doses of carbamate pesticides to soil upto 30

days of application, reached a maximum value with 0.25 g kg⁻¹ of soil of pesticide I; 0.2 g kg⁻¹ of soil of pesticide II and 0.3 g kg⁻¹ of soil as pesticide III, and then declined with time and concentration.

The average of replicated values for water-soluble, exchangeable, active, reducible Mn, exchangeable, available Fe, EC, pH and E_h are recorded in Tables 2-10. An examination of data (Tables 2-5) indicates that the water-soluble, exchangeable and active Mn increased significantly in the presence of carbamate pesticides (I, II, III) as compared to blank and reached a maximum value at 30 days of incubation and then declined. The maximum value is reached with 0.25 g kg⁻¹ soil for pesticide I, with 0.2 g kg⁻¹ for pesticide II, and with 0.3 g kg⁻¹ for pesticide III. The dose order for water soluble Mn was $t_3 > t_2 > t_4 > t_6 > t_1 > t_0$ for pesticide I; $t_2 > t_3 > t_4 > t_1 > t_5 > t_6 > t_0$ for pesticide II and $t_4 > t_3 > t_2 > t_5 > t_1 > t_6 > t_0$ for pesticide III. It was also found that within 30 days, the exchangeable Mn and active Mn increased from 9.3 to 27.0, 74.1 to 84.6; 10.0 to 27.7, 74.0 to 85.0; 9.6 to 29.4, 74.1 to 86.2 with 0.25 mg kg⁻¹ of pesticide I, 0.2 g of pesticide II and 0.3 g kg⁻¹ soil of pesticide III, respectively.

The mechanism by which an increase in the availability of water-soluble, available and active Mn occurred in fumigated soil has been reported⁹. The simultaneous increase in concentration of three forms of Mn and then decrease in concentration in presence of different doses of

Table 2. Effect of carbamate pesticides on water soluble Mn of soil with variation in concentration and time

Dose in g per kg of soil	Water-soluble Mn in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
<i>Oxamyl</i>								
0.0	3.62	4.15	5.96	5.12	4.88	4.03	3.87	4.52
0.1	3.62	6.04	8.18	7.05	5.94	5.62	5.02	5.92
0.2	3.60	7.55	9.77	8.10	7.82	6.90	6.01	7.11
0.25	3.60	8.66	11.20	10.06	9.01	8.45	7.24	8.33
0.3	3.66	7.22	9.50	8.46	7.41	6.56	5.54	6.91
0.4	3.66	6.52	8.02	7.92	6.62	5.66	5.32	6.25
0.5	3.65	5.86	7.04	6.86	5.61	4.54	4.04	5.37
Average	3.63	6.57	8.53	7.66	6.75	5.97	5.29	
LSD for days	0.29							
LSD for doses	0.30							
<i>S-Ethyl-N-methyl(carbamoyloxy)thioacetamidate</i>								
0.0	3.62	4.20	5.88	5.19	4.88	4.00	3.85	4.52
0.1	3.90	6.34	8.98	7.86	6.74	6.46	5.92	6.60
0.2	4.08	8.44	10.56	8.92	8.45	7.77	6.82	7.87
0.25	3.90	8.30	10.32	8.80	8.40	7.70	6.46	7.69
0.3	3.66	7.10	9.34	8.32	7.30	6.42	5.45	6.80
0.4	3.66	6.24	7.54	7.26	6.22	5.32	5.02	5.89
0.5	3.60	5.48	6.64	6.44	5.41	4.12	4.02	5.11
Average	3.77	6.59	8.47	7.54	6.77	5.97	5.36	
LSD for days	0.31							
LSD for doses	0.28							
<i>N-Phenyl(ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate</i>								
0.0	3.62	4.25	5.97	5.28	4.98	4.06	3.82	4.57
0.1	3.62	6.12	8.67	7.68	6.50	6.24	5.06	6.27
0.2	3.68	8.02	10.12	8.62	8.00	7.18	6.45	7.44
0.25	3.72	8.52	10.78	8.88	8.50	7.86	7.12	7.91
0.3	3.80	8.80	11.00	9.24	8.75	8.12	7.12	8.12
0.4	3.70	7.25	9.50	8.20	7.45	6.66	5.55	6.90
0.5	3.60	5.64	6.88	6.62	5.55	4.32	4.12	5.24
Average	3.60	6.94	8.99	7.79	7.10	6.35	5.61	
LSD for days	0.28							
LSD for doses	0.32							

pesticide was due to both biological and chemical reasons¹⁰. The soil collected from different places of Aligarh was found to contain hard nodular concretions of magniferous¹² deposits. As the soil was wetted in presence of carbamate pesticide the enhanced effect (Table 1) of actinomycetes, ascomycetes and reinfested fungus flora *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizobium*, *Thiobacillus thiooxidans*, etc. resulted in a change of oxidation-reduction potential of the soil system; in the release of carboxylic acid and producing solubilizing effect which brought about a gradual change in water-soluble and available Mn^{II} in the soil. These inferences were supported by decrease in pH and increase in E_h and EC values as the concentration goes on in-

creasing during 30 days of application of pesticide (Tables 8-10). These observations are in the line of work of other workers^{13,14} too. With the toxic effect of higher doses of chemicals on soil microorganism and soil enzyme, the stimulated effect declined after a certain period and the equilibrium shifted towards Mn^{IV} resulting in increase of pH. The declining effect with passage of time, however, was due to rapid utilization of organic chemicals as an energy source, by re-establishment of pesticide-sensitive Mn oxidizing bacteria, such as *Bacillus*, *Streptomyces*, *Aerobacter* etc. (Table 1) which converts Mn^{II} to Mn^{IV}. The view was in accordance with the observation of Charles and Paul¹³.

Table 3. Effect of carbamate pesticides on exchangeable Mn of soil with variation in concentration and time

Dose in g per kg of soil	Exchangeable Mn in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
<i>Oxamyl</i>								
0.0	9.32	16.12	17.66	15.98	14.06	12.84	12.36	14.05
0.1	9.30	17.44	18.94	16.90	15.88	14.72	13.14	15.19
0.2	9.34	20.24	23.30	21.02	18.72	17.35	16.88	18.12
0.25	9.26	24.12	27.06	24.26	21.74	19.68	18.04	20.59
0.3	9.34	21.62	23.14	21.16	20.10	18.68	17.44	18.78
0.4	9.28	19.16	20.62	19.86	17.58	16.45	15.33	16.90
0.5	9.30	15.65	17.82	16.52	14.66	13.20	12.34	14.21
Average	9.31	19.19	21.25	19.39	17.53	16.13	15.08	
LSD for days	1.22							
LSD for doses	0.91							
<i>S-Ethyl-N-methyl(carbamoyloxy)thioacetamide</i>								
0.0	9.32	15.42	18.38	15.90	14.64	13.22	12.50	14.20
0.1	9.82	18.54	21.44	18.94	17.88	16.72	15.28	16.93
0.2	9.96	22.64	27.74	21.52	19.86	18.22	19.94	19.59
0.25	9.90	22.20	26.90	20.78	19.20	17.77	16.22	19.06
0.3	9.72	20.22	22.76	19.96	18.12	17.02	16.22	17.70
0.4	9.46	18.00	19.72	18.00	16.60	15.52	14.76	16.02
0.5	9.32	16.86	18.62	17.12	15.46	14.00	13.12	14.93
Average	9.64	19.14	22.22	18.89	17.38	16.04	15.01	
LSD for days	1.12							
LSD for doses	1.03							
<i>N-Phenyl(ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate</i>								
0.0	9.32	15.70	17.02	15.62	14.02	12.78	12.14	13.82
0.1	9.46	16.74	18.12	16.20	15.02	13.80	12.84	14.60
0.2	9.22	20.78	25.14	21.92	19.45	18.00	17.02	18.78
0.25	9.30	24.14	28.14	24.84	22.48	20.42	18.96	21.18
0.3	9.56	25.24	29.36	25.43	23.22	21.16	19.48	21.92
0.4	9.30	21.56	25.06	22.00	20.12	19.24	17.08	19.12
0.5	9.00	18.52	21.34	19.00	17.12	16.12	15.14	16.62
Average	9.31	20.31	23.45	20.72	18.77	17.36	16.10	
LSD for days	1.06							
LSD for doses	1.23							

As in the case of Mn, the concentration of exchangeable and available Fe (Tables 6 and 7) were also increased significantly with the addition of carbamate pesticides and reached a maximum value with 0.25 g kg⁻¹ soil for pesticide I; 0.2 g kg⁻¹ soil for pesticide II and 0.3 g kg⁻¹ soil for pesticide III in 30 days of their application and then

declined. The increase was from 13.1 to 30.0 mg kg⁻¹ in case of exchangeable Fe and 66.0 from 45.1 mg kg⁻¹ in case of available Fe. Increase in available and exchangeable Fe may be due to microbial decomposition of organic matter with liberation of acids, the increase in oxidation-reduction potential in moist conditions of the soil, stimulation in the

Table 4. Effect of carbamate pesticides on reducible Mn of soil with variation in concentration and time

Dose in g per kg of soil	Reducible Mn in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
<i>Oxamyl</i>								
0.0	60.70	54.85	52.94	53.18	55.06	56.05	56.69	55.64
0.1	61.06	53.64	52.65	53.81	54.18	54.28	55.68	55.05
0.2	61.20	53.45	49.93	51.30	52.38	51.99	53.35	53.51
0.25	61.28	49.56	46.34	47.30	49.31	51.33	52.36	51.19
0.3	60.98	52.16	50.78	50.80	50.13	51.20	53.26	52.52
0.4	61.04	54.32	53.88	51.94	52.74	53.32	54.49	54.39
0.5	61.69	55.25	52.94	52.48	53.70	55.91	57.27	55.33
Average	60.99	53.18	51.32	51.53	52.50	53.60	54.73	
LSD for days	0.65							
LSD for doses	0.68							
<i>S-Ethyl-N-methyl(carbamoyloxy)thioacetamide</i>								
0.0	60.70	54.62	51.74	52.91	53.72	55.92	56.79	55.19
0.1	60.14	53.64	51.02	52.22	52.02	52.49	53.80	53.49
0.2	59.94	51.68	46.70	52.06	50.45	51.87	52.58	52.14
0.25	60.00	51.96	47.56	52.84	51.22	52.19	53.68	52.74
0.3	60.48	51.68	51.92	51.72	51.30	53.26	54.67	53.79
0.4	60.52	53.72	52.54	52.14	51.63	53.61	54.24	54.10
0.5	60.72	53.66	52.82	52.24	53.01	55.76	56.54	55.02
Average	60.37	53.26	50.47	52.16	51.47	53.61	54.61	
LSD for days	0.62							
LSD for doses	0.69							
<i>N-Phenyl(ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate</i>								
0.0	61.00	54.09	54.09	52.72	54.24	55.90	56.78	55.20
0.1	60.58	52.20	50.33	50.79	52.48	53.08	54.84	53.48
0.2	60.76	51.44	46.82	48.72	50.17	50.92	52.03	51.59
0.25	60.96	50.40	46.22	48.38	48.28	50.56	51.92	50.97
0.3	60.78	49.58	45.80	48.47	48.03	49.94	51.40	50.57
0.4	60.98	51.77	48.46	49.86	49.45	50.66	53.87	52.10
0.5	61.04	53.12	50.90	51.14	52.45	53.68	54.74	53.86
Average	61.85	51.80	48.66	50.02	50.73	52.11	52.57	
LSD for days	0.61							
LSD for doses	0.66							

activity of microorganisms by the pesticides extending upto a period of 4 weeks and a favourable pH¹⁵ (Table 1). The above inferences were supported by decrease in pH with

addition of carbamate pesticides and time interval (Table 7). With dissipation of the organic chemical, the stimulatory effects declined and with Fe bacteria taking

Table 5. Effect of carbamate pesticides on active manganese of soil with variation in concentration and time

Dose in g per kg of soil	Active Mn in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
<i>Oxamyl</i>								
0.0	73.64	75.12	76.56	74.28	74.00	72.92	72.92	74.21
0.1	73.98	77.12	79.77	77.76	76.00	74.62	73.84	76.16
0.2	74.14	81.24	83.00	80.42	78.92	77.24	76.24	78.74
0.25	74.14	82.34	84.60	81.62	80.04	79.46	77.64	80.01
0.3	73.98	81.00	83.42	80.42	77.64	76.44	76.24	78.31
0.4	73.98	80.00	82.52	79.72	76.94	75.54	75.14	77.54
0.5	73.64	75.76	77.80	75.86	73.97	73.65	73.65	74.91
Average	73.93	78.94	81.10	78.58	76.79	75.70	75.10	
LSD for days	0.96							
LSD for doses	1.03							
<i>S-Ethyl-N-methyl(carbomoyloxy)thioacetamide</i>								
0.0	73.64	74.24	76.00	74.00	73.24	73.14	73.14	73.91
0.1	73.86	78.52	81.44	78.02	76.64	75.65	75.00	77.02
0.2	73.98	82.76	85.00	82.50	78.76	77.86	76.34	79.60
0.25	73.86	82.46	84.78	82.42	78.82	77.66	76.34	79.49
0.3	73.86	81.00	83.02	80.00	77.12	76.72	76.34	78.29
0.4	73.64	77.96	79.80	77.40	74.82	74.45	74.02	76.01
0.5	73.64	76.00	78.08	75.80	74.34	73.88	73.68	75.06
Average	73.78	78.99	81.16	78.59	76.68	75.62	74.98	
LSD for days	0.95							
LSD for doses	1.02							
<i>N-Phenyl(ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate</i>								
0.0	73.64	74.04	75.08	73.62	73.24	72.74	72.74	73.79
0.1	73.64	75.06	77.12	74.77	74.00	73.12	72.74	74.35
0.2	73.86	80.24	82.08	79.26	77.62	76.10	75.50	77.81
0.25	73.98	83.06	85.14	82.10	79.26	78.84	78.00	80.06
0.3	74.14	83.62	86.16	83.14	80.00	79.22	78.00	80.61
0.4	73.98	80.08	83.02	80.06	77.02	76.56	76.00	78.12
0.5	73.64	77.28	79.12	76.76	75.12	74.12	74.00	75.12
Average	73.84	79.05	81.10	78.53	76.61	75.82	75.28	
LSD for days	0.95							
LSD for doses	1.04							

over (Table 1), both the forms of Fe suffered a declining effect. Similar results were reported earlier^{3,16}.

An examination of the correlation coefficients (Table 11) for all the three studied carbamate pesticides revealed

that water soluble Mn, exchangeable Mn, exchangeable Fe, available Fe, E_n and EC were all positively correlated with each other and negatively correlated with reducible Mn and pH pointing to an almost similar mechanism for their variations in the soil.

Table 10. Effect of carbamate pesticides on electrode potential of soil with variation in concentration and time

Dose in g per kg of soil	E_h (mV) at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
	Oxamyl							
0.0	40.2	41.1	42.6	41.8	41.0	40.6	40.0	40.9
0.1	40.2	42.1	44.6	43.8	41.6	40.6	40.0	41.8
0.2	40.8	43.2	47.0	45.1	42.4	41.2	40.0	42.8
0.25	40.8	44.0	48.5	46.0	43.2	42.1	41.0	43.7
0.3	40.2	43.4	47.2	45.0	42.8	41.2	40.6	42.9
0.4	40.5	42.7	45.2	44.2	42.0	40.4	40.6	42.2
0.5	40.2	42.5	44.1	43.6	42.0	40.3	40.4	41.9
Average	40.4	42.7	45.5	44.2	42.1	40.9	40.4	
LSD for days	0.75							
LSD for doses	0.66							
	S-Ethyl-N-methyl(carbamoyloxy)thioacetamide							
0.0	40.2	41.0	41.6	41.6	41.2	40.6	40.4	40.9
0.1	40.6	42.4	44.2	43.2	41.8	41.2	41.0	42.1
0.2	40.8	43.8	46.2	45.0	42.8	42.0	41.6	43.2
0.25	40.8	43.6	45.8	44.2	42.0	41.0	41.0	42.6
0.3	40.5	43.0	44.2	43.1	41.0	40.1	40.0	41.7
0.4	40.4	42.2	43.0	42.5	41.0	40.0	40.0	41.3
0.5	40.2	41.0	42.0	42.0	40.8	40.2	39.8	40.8
Average	40.5	42.4	43.9	43.1	41.5	40.7	40.5	
LSD for days	0.78							
LSD for doses	0.74							
	N-Phenyl(ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate							
0.0	40.2	41.0	41.2	41.2	41.0	40.6	40.2	40.8
0.1	40.2	41.6	42.1	41.9	41.2	41.0	40.8	41.3
0.2	40.5	42.4	43.0	42.6	42.0	41.2	41.0	41.8
0.25	40.6	43.4	45.0	44.0	43.0	42.2	41.6	42.8
0.3	40.8	43.8	45.6	44.4	43.2	42.8	42.2	43.3
0.4	40.5	43.2	44.2	43.8	43.0	42.0	41.2	42.5
0.5	40.2	42.6	43.2	42.6	42.0	41.0	40.6	41.7
Average	40.4	42.6	43.5	42.9	42.2	41.5	41.1	
LSD for days	0.72							
LSD for doses	0.70							

Table 11. Correlation coefficients in between different forms of manganese, iron, pH, EC and redox potential (E_h) for three carbamate pesticides

Form	Exchangeable Mn	Reducible Mn	Exchangeable Fe	Available Fe	pH	EC	E_h
	Oxamyl						
Water soluble Mn	0.972	-0.953	0.985	0.955	-0.883	0.981	0.982
Exchangeable Mn	-	-0.983	0.977	0.918	-0.864	0.966	0.965
Reducible Mn	-	-	-0.939	-0.940	0.880	-0.972	-0.970
Exchangeable Fe	-	-	-	0.904	-0.845	0.948	0.945
Available Fe	-	-	-	-	-0.965	0.952	0.950
pH	-	-	-	-	-	-0.919	-0.815
EC	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.948
	S-Ethyl-N-methyl(carbamoyloxy)thioacetamide						
Water soluble Mn	0.994	-0.966	0.952	0.964	-0.894	0.966	0.972
Exchangeable Mn	-	-0.967	0.970	0.975	-0.872	0.956	0.950
Reducible Mn	-	-	-0.984	-0.983	0.906	-0.972	-0.968
Exchangeable Fe	-	-	-	0.991	-0.888	0.946	0.945
Available Fe	-	-	-	-	-0.865	0.936	0.935
pH	-	-	-	-	-	-0.906	-0.824
EC	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.936
	N-Phenyl(ethylcarbamoyl)propylcarbamate						
Water soluble Mn	0.893	-0.978	0.984	0.971	-0.886	0.972	0.976
Exchangeable Mn	-	-0.958	0.944	0.966	-0.914	0.956	0.962
Reducible Mn	-	-	-0.991	-0.997	0.900	-0.962	-0.945
Exchangeable Fe	-	-	-	0.985	-0.912	0.952	0.912
Available Fe	-	-	-	-	-0.886	0.916	0.900
pH	-	-	-	-	-	-0.910	-0.816
EC	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.926

The results also denote that the effectiveness of studied carbamate pesticides is in the order : **II** > **I** > **III**. The dissipation of all the three carbamate pesticides start after a gap of 30 days.

Experimental

The soil (depth 0-30 cm) was collected from Aligarh district. The soil contained 0.62% organic carbon, its pH (1 : 2.5) was 8.4 and the electrical conductivity (1 : 2.5) 0.31 dS m⁻¹. $E_h = 40.2$ mV, ESP = 21.5, CEC = 9.8 cmol (p⁺ kg⁻¹). Water soluble, exchangeable, reducible Mn, exchangeable and available Fe were 3.6, 9.3, 60.7, 13.8 and 46 mg kg⁻¹, respectively.

The experiments were done in triplicate in earthenware pots (60 × 45 cm) lined with polyethene sheet in triplicate. Each pot was filled with 5 kg of soil, the soil was treated with seven levels (0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 g kg⁻¹ soil, t₀ to t₆) of three carbamate pesticides (**I**, **II**, **III**) separately. All the samples were then watered upto the water holding capacity with distilled water. The pots were then watered weekly throughout the course of the experiments to make up for the loss of weight (due to evaporation) on standing.

The treated samples were drawn periodically by a soil sampler at intervals of 15 days and analyzed spectrophotometrically for water-soluble, exchangeable, reducible Mn, exchangeable and available Fe. The pH, EC, organic carbon were determined by the method as discussed elsewhere⁷. Water-soluble, exchangeable and reducible Mn were estimated¹⁷ at 525 nm, and exchangeable and available Fe by reported method¹⁸ at 490 nm. The values of redox potential (E_h) were determined using platinum electrode by pH meter. Correlation coefficients between water-soluble, exchangeable, reducible Mn, available, exchangeable Fe, pH, E_h and EC were also calculated.

To study the effect of different doses carbamate pesticides on microbial growth, bacterial and fungal counts were estimated at different time intervals by serial dilution and plating technique. In each case three replicates were taken. The values are given in Table 1.

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